

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
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**ВЕСТНИК ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ И
КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF THE RESULTS OF SURGICAL, LASER AND CONSERVATIVE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH PHACOGENIC GLAUCOMA DURING A LONG-TERM OBSERVATION PERIOD

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Resume. Phacogenic glaucoma is a large group of eye diseases characterized by an increase in intraocular pressure beyond the level tolerable for the optic nerve, glaucomatous optic neuropathy and a typical decrease in visual functions. The aim of the study was to investigate and compare the results of conservative, laser and surgical treatment of patients with phacogenic glaucoma during long-term observation. The study was conducted in the eye department and inpatient clinic of the multidisciplinary clinic of Samarkand State Medical University. 58 patients were under observation. In the treatment of patients, conservative methods of hypotensive treatment prevail (51.2%) over modern laser (4.3%) and surgical (12.1%) techniques. In 28% of patients, there was an unjustifiably long conservative treatment and their late referral for surgery, and 38% of patients were not offered surgical treatment at all. Surgical treatment was carried out mainly in the late stages of the disease: 5% in stage I, 58% in stage II, and 62.5% in stage III. General outpatient treatment was carried out in 37% of patients, and inpatient treatment was carried out only in 4.6%, despite the fact that 72% had concomitant pathology.

Key words: phacogenic glaucoma, conservative treatment, laser treatment, surgical treatment, long-term observation, intraocular pressure.

УЗОҚ МУДДАТЛИ КУЗАТУВ ДАВРИДА ФАКОГЕН ГЛАУКОМА БИЛАН ОҒРИГАН БЕМОРЛАРНИ ЖАРРОҲЛИК, ЛАЗЕР ВА КОНСЕРВАТИВ ДАВОЛАШ НАТИЖАЛАРИНИ ҚИЁСИЙ БАҲОЛАШ

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Резюме. Факоген глаукома кўз ичибосимининг кўрув нерви учун тоқат қилинадиган даражадан ошиб кетиши, глаукоматоз оптик нейропатия ва кўриш функцияларининг одатий пасайиши билан тавсифланган кўз касалликларининг катта гуруҳидир. Тадқиқотнинг мақсади узоқ муддатли кузатув пайтида факоген глаукома билан оғриган беморларни консерватив, лазер ва жарроҳлик даволаш натижаларини ўрганиш ва таққослаш эди. Тадқиқот Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети кўп тармоқли клиникасининг офтальмология бўлими ва стационар клиникасида ўтказилди. 58 нафар бемор кузатув остида эди. Беморларни даволашда замонавий лазер (4,3%) ва жарроҳлик (12,1%) усулларига нисбатан гипотензив даволашнинг консерватив усуллари (51,2%) устунлик қилади. Беморларнинг 28 фоизда консерватив даво асосиз узоқ давом этганлиги ва уларни жарроҳлик амалиётига кеч юбориш ҳолатлари кузатилган, беморларнинг 38 фоизда эса умуман жарроҳлик даволаш таклиф этилмаган. Жарроҳлик даволаш асосан касалликнинг кечки босқичларида амалга оширилди: I босқичда 5%, II босқичда 58%, III босқичда 62,5%. Беморларнинг 37 фоизда умумий амбулатор даволаниш, 72 фоизда ҳамроҳ бўлган патология бўлганига қарамай, 4,6 фоиз стационар даволаниш амалга оширилган.

Калит сўзлар: факоген глаукома, консерватив даво, лазер билан даволаш, жарроҳлик даволаш, узоқ муддатли кузатиш, кўз ичи босими.

СРАВНИТЕЛЬНАЯ ОЦЕНКА РЕЗУЛЬТАТОВ ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОГО, ЛАЗЕРНОГО И КОНСЕРВАТИВНОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ПАЦИЕНТОВ С ФАКОГЕННОЙ ГЛАУКОМОЙ ПРИ ДЛИТЕЛЬНОМ ПЕРИОДЕ НАБЛЮДЕНИЯ

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Резюме. Факогенная глаукома - большая группа заболеваний глаза, характеризующаяся повышением внутриглазного давления за пределы толерантного для зрительного нерва уровня, глаукомной оптической нейропатией и типичным снижением зрительных функций. Целью исследования было изучение и сравнение результатов консервативного, лазерного и хирургического лечения пациентов факогенной глаукомой при длительном наблюдении. Исследование проводилось в глазном от-

делении и стационарной поликлиники многопрофильной клиники Самаркандского Государственного Медицинского Университета. Под наблюдением находилось 58 пациентов. В лечении больных преобладают консервативные методы гипотензивного лечения (51,2%) над современными лазерными (4,3%) и хирургическими (12,1%) методиками. У 28% больных имело место неоправданно длительное консервативное лечение и позднее направление их на операцию, а 38% больных оперативное лечение совсем не предлагалось. Оперативное лечение проводилось в основном в поздние стадии заболевания: в I стадии 5%, во II - 58% и в III - 62,5%. Общее лечение в амбулаторных условиях проведено у 37% больных, а стационарное - только у 4,6%, притом, что у 72% выявлена сопутствующая патология.

Ключевые слова: факогенная глаукома, консервативное лечение, лазерное лечение, хирургическое лечение, длительное наблюдение, внутриглазное давление.

Actuality of the problem. Despite the progress in treatment methods, glaucoma remains one of the main causes of vision loss and irreversible blindness. According to the World Health Organization, about 67 million people in the world suffer from glaucoma, and by 2030 this number of patients should double[2]. The prevalence of this dangerous disease increases with age. Thus, at 40-45 years of age, 1% of the population suffers from primary open-angle glaucoma (POAG), at 50-60 - 1.5-2%, at 75 years and older - more than 18%[4]. Such threatening statistics indicate objective difficulties associated with both diagnosis and treatment of this disease. Phacogenic glaucoma is a large group of eye diseases characterized by an increase in intraocular pressure beyond the level tolerable for the optic nerve, glaucomatous optic neuropathy and a typical decrease in visual functions[6]. The presence of a high level of intraocular pressure (IOP) leads to the accelerated development of glaucomatous optic neuropathy and a decrease in visual functions[7]. The main direction in the treatment of phacogenic glaucoma is an effective and rational reduction of IOP (conservative, laser or surgical methods), which should be supplemented by courses of supportive conservative therapy. The choice of a method for reducing IOP is individual and depends on many factors, but in most patients with phacogenic glaucoma, treatment begins with a conservative method of reducing IOP, by selecting one or more drugs for local use, which should be used by the patient in accordance with the prescribed regimen. In recent years, non-penetrating surgeries have become increasingly common in phacogenic glaucoma surgery. They are virtually complication-free but have inferior hypotensive results to fistulizing surgeries. The surgical approach to treating phacogenic glaucoma continues to be an alternative when drug therapy is ineffective. A decrease in IOP after surgery affects the functional state of the eye. Central and peripheral vision, the state of the optical system, and most importantly, the retina and optic nerve change. After antiglaucoma surgeries, many patients experience some expansion of the visual field, improved dark adaptation, color and contrast sensitivity. However, continuous long-term observations of the dynamics of visual functions in patients with phacogenic glaucoma lead to the conclusion that there is no progress in combating this disease[8]. Indeed, the chronic course of the disease, the unreliability of some seemingly traditional approaches to treatment, and a significant number of negative outcomes support this conclusion. Some advances in modern drug, laser and surgical hypotensive treatment of phacogenic glaucoma do not, however, provide the opportunity to reliably predict its remote functional results. The choice of tactics for managing patients with phacogenic glaucoma is the most important and complex stage of dispensary observation. Until now, there are no methods that allow us to determine with a high degree of probability the nature of the outcome of the treatment used in patients with phacogenic glaucoma. Comparative assessment of the results of conservative, laser and surgical treatment of phacogenic glaucoma is an important task in ophthalmology. All of the above determines the relevance of this work.

The purpose of the study is to study and compare the results of conservative, laser and surgical treatment of patients with phacogenic glaucoma during long-term observation.

Materials and methods of research. The study was conducted in the eye department and inpatient clinic of the multidisciplinary clinic of the Samarkand State Medical University. 58 patients were under observation. The following examination methods were performed on the patients: visometry, computer perimetry, pneumotometry, optical coherence tomography, tonography. All patients were divided into 2 groups: the first group received only complex conservative treatment, the second group received, in addition to conservative treatment, surgical treatment: laser and FEK + IOL surgery. Laser and surgical interventions were used only in the second and third stages of treatment of phacogenic glaucoma. In this case, the indications for surgical treatment were insufficient effectiveness of drug therapy, namely hypotensive therapy, the inability of the patient to systematically visit an ophthalmologist, the patient's carelessness in following the ophthalmologist's instructions. At the same time, surgical intervention can be performed at any stage of glaucoma in accordance with the choice of the attending physician and only in the case of informed consent of the patient. Laser interventions are safer and can be performed on an outpatient basis, but provide a limited and

not always stable hypotensive effect. Surgical "knife" operations are more effective, but at the same time are characterized by significant trauma. The action of lasers is based either on the application of a local burn to the trabecular zone with subsequent atrophy and scarring of tissue (coagulator lasers), or on a microexplosion, which is accompanied by a rupture of tissue and a shock wave (destructor lasers)

Results and discussion. According to the study, the diagnosis of phacogenic glaucoma in 47.4% of cases was established upon patient's request, in 45.9% - when the patient sought help for another disease, and only in 6.7% of cases during a preventive examination. Phacogenic glaucoma is often detected during professional examinations in 35% of cases, and in 65% - when patients directly contact an ophthalmologist. Moreover, only 43% of patients consulted an ophthalmologist immediately after the first signs characteristic of glaucoma, and 39% - 2-3 years after the first symptoms of the disease. Every eleventh patient (9%) consulted an ophthalmologist already at an advanced (6.6%) or terminal (2.4%) stage. Of interest is the use of the so-called selective screening method in the study of the population. The advantages of "glaucoma screening" are the absence of the need for hospitalization for examination, its short duration, high efficiency of timely treatment and the possibility of reducing the percentage (5.71%) of surgical interventions with timely detection of the disease. Diagnosis of glaucoma dictates the need for lifelong medical examination of this group of patients. Only 37.1% of patients regularly visited the doctor on dispensary days. It was also revealed that 14.5% of patients in the dispensary group were observed by the ophthalmologist irregularly and did not fully comply with his instructions, and 2% did not comply with them at all. In the treatment of patients, conservative methods of hypotensive treatment prevail (51.2%) over modern laser (4.3%) and surgical (12.1%) methods. In 28% of patients, there was an unjustifiably long conservative treatment and late referral for surgery, and 38% of patients were not offered surgical treatment at all. Surgical treatment was carried out mainly in the late stages of the disease: 5% in stage I, 58% in stage II and 62.5% in stage III. General treatment in outpatient settings was carried out in 37% of patients, and inpatient treatment - only in 4.6%, despite the fact that 72% were diagnosed with concomitant pathology.

Conclusion. Thus, the arsenal of modern drug, laser, surgical types of treatment of phacogenic glaucoma is quite diverse, however, no matter how good and effective they are, without a special contribution of the patient with phacogenic glaucoma to his hypotensive treatment, there will be no success in it anyway. It follows that too much responsibility and burden for impeccable compliance with the regimen of instillation of eye drops and observation lies with the patient himself. After all, under certain circumstances, patients with phacogenic glaucoma may simply not instill eye drops, refuse laser or surgical operations, that is, simply not be treated. An imperfect system of dispensary observation, as well as insufficiently effective treatment of patients with phacogenic glaucoma lead to a progressive deterioration of visual functions and the transition of the disease to a more severe stage, which in turn causes an increase in the number of blind and visually impaired people who have become disabled due to glaucoma.

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